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GAMEHEARTS

Prototype Report

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- Grant Agreement:** 101132543 - HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01
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1. Project Summary

GAMEHEARTS seeks to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This considers the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between more the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium offers policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out how the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It will utilise an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a holistic ecosystem approach, utilising both established and more innovative methodologies, to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and how video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In doing so, GAMEHEARTS will develop ‘ludic experiences’, to explore possibilities of more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland) will work in partnership with Ubisoft (France) and other major video game partners and associations (including the VGE & EGDF) to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE. Beyond this, we work with certain cultural case studies partners to consider the ways in which game-related technologies and practices are, and could be used to, increase access to heritage, the arts, and sport.

2. Introduction

This report presents an innovative approach to addressing the social inclusion of youth by developing player-centred video game prototypes aimed at fostering social engagement and personal growth. This work targets the intersection of video game design and social impact, exploring how gameful experiences can bridge social divides, enhance personal skills, and promote social cohesion. It emphasises the importance of social inclusion, particularly in today's digital age, where youth face challenges of marginalisation, isolation, and limited engagement opportunities. Social inclusion here means more than participation; it encompasses youth empowerment, resilience, and the development of a sense of belonging within their communities. The European Union's Youth Strategy advocates for tools that engage youth in meaningful ways, helping them realise their potential as active citizens. Given the widespread appeal and interactivity of video games, we see gamification as an untapped resource for promoting these social values. By embedding aspects of Positive Youth Development (PYD) within video game mechanics, these player-centred prototypes could represent a transformative means for youths to cultivate skills like confidence, connection, and compassion in a socially engaging and enjoyable format. As Section 2.1 further details, the report recognises the unique position of video games to combat youth exclusion through motivation, collaboration, and play. These prototypes do not merely entertain but strategically use gameplay to engage youth in self-reflection, community involvement, and cooperation, leveraging game mechanics to support the developmental needs of the youth, particularly those at risk of marginalisation. This approach seeks to create a socially responsible gaming environment that reinforces the potential of young people and empowers them as both learners and contributors to society. Through the lens of inclusion, the report illustrates the development process, theoretical framework, and implementation of prototypes designed to embody this vision.

2.1 Social Inclusion of Youth

Social inclusion of youth implies integration into a social community by means of occupation or study, personal realisation of the youth in said community and a structural acceptance of the youth's potential. Social inclusion can be portrayed as a multi-faceted spectrum ranging from marginalisation and isolation, on the one end, and active participation on the other, across dimensions such as economic, political, cultural and social (Kovacheva, 2014). The EU Youth Strategy highlights the importance of enabling youth to realise their own skills and potentials to be engaged citizens and develop resilience as well as actively drive social change (European Commission, 2018).

Gamified tools have been shown to be helpful in addressing youth inclusion from different aspects; gamified tools have been developed to motivate civic engagement among youth (Culén et al., 2015), and game-based learning has been used for vocational training (Dahalan et al., 2024) as well as career adaptability (Hummel et al., 2018). Gamified platforms have also been developed to motivate unemployed youth to engage in job-seeking activities (Mattila et al., 2018). In youth work contexts, gamification and games have been recognised as a fruitful tool for fostering inclusion through a combination of motivational and social factors; gamification can motivate active involvement and learning, and playing digital games together can foster connection and a sense of belonging (YEU, 2021). Thus, the utilisation of gamified methods in youth work activities holds potential for addressing the social inclusion of youth both through developmental and social lenses.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Positive Youth Development (PYD) is a framework of youth development that views youth as individuals with skills, strengths and potentials to be nurtured and developed within a social context (Lerner, 2009). Person-context interactions, facilitated by youth programs, bring about five distinct behaviours (5 C's) that can enable youth to transcend onto a trajectory of personal thriving, well-being and contribution (Lerner et al., 2005). The 5 C's are competence, confidence, connection, character, and caring. Competence relates to the youth's view of their own skills and action in social, academic, cognitive and vocational areas. This can be interpersonal skills, decision-making skills, grades, work and career habits. Confidence is the view of self-worth and self-efficacy. Connection represents reciprocal bonds with friends, family and institutions. Character implies an inner moral compass with respect for social values. Caring and compassion means sympathy and empathy for others (Roth & Brooks-Gunn, 2003; Lerner et al., 2005).

Figure 1. A developmental contextual view of PYD (Lerner et al. 2005).

2.3 Aim

The aim of this endeavour is to design and develop a hybrid game (digital and real-life interaction) to cultivate personal and shared development through the framework of PYD and the 5 C's. The game functions as an interface for meeting and connecting with others in a social context while exploring crucial skills needed to contribute to self, to society and thrive, thereby addressing social inclusion. Careful needs analysis in terms of practical challenges and needs will guide the development of the game.

3. Ideation and Design Process

The prototype design process was carried out in three stages: 1) needs assessment, to discover the needs of the target group and the specific aim of the prototype (including the identification of the relevant research frameworks); 2) first design workshop with game designers, to ideate and create possible concepts and narratives suitable for the target group and achieving of the set aim; and 3) second design workshop with Gamification Group's research design team, to develop the game scenario that will be prototyped.

3.1 Needs Assessment

To be able to better understand and address the needs of the target group, we first identified a partner, a youth work centre in Helsinki experienced in youth inclusion. The youth centre implements targeted gaming activities primarily for people aged 15 to 25. Activities of the space are open to all young people and young adults regardless of their socio-economic and cultural background, gender identity, sexual orientation or neurodiversity. Their work is based on the principle of safe space, and follows values such as equality, equity and human rights, with the participation in the activities being voluntary, open, free of charge and accessible.

The information session with representatives of the said centre took place online via MS Teams on September 27, 2024, lasting one hour. Apart from the GAMEHEARTS researchers, three youth workers responsible for hosting the game events from the centre participated in the meeting. The youth workers coordinate and facilitate the youth work centre's activities such as game nights and game dev-clubs. They also help the youth with any general things they might need assistance with, such as navigating Kela (Finnish Social Insurance Institution). When their own knowledge is insufficient to help with the issue at hand, they refer the youth to more suitable experts and professionals. We discussed the relation of our research topic and prototype idea with their work, and how our goals align with their needs and working context. The main goals that the research centre has, in terms of youth inclusion, are bringing together marginalised and non-marginalised youth (e.g., neurodivergent and LGBTQIA+ people), decreasing loneliness, supporting youth employment and opportunities for education and training as well as enhancement of media literacy skills. The main challenges they are faced with are skill imbalance regarding gaming proficiency as well basic technical skills among young people and language barriers. On the other hand, when it comes to sharing their

perspective on the challenges young people of Helsinki are faced with in the modern society, participants mentioned issues related to understand and navigate the Finnish bureaucracy, how to be able to earn a living wage, improve physical and mental wellbeing (sleeping habits, managing stress levels, participating in physical activities) as well as increase the general declining feeling of hope.

Although it was acknowledged that the game prototype could not cover all of the topics mentioned above, the meeting provided us with a better understanding of the youth as our target group and laid out the foundation for the game prototype (and later the full game development), in terms of the aim of the game, the intended user(s) as well as the theoretical framework which will be used for the design process.

As a result of this section, it was agreed that the main aim of the workshop would be to ideate narrative concepts and mechanics of a gameful tool in youth work that increases inclusion and fosters community among marginalised and non-marginalised youth.

3.2 First Design Workshop

The second stage in the prototype design process was a 2-hour workshop with game designers that took place on October 15, 2024, also online via MS Teams. Aside from two GAMEHEARTS researchers, four game designers participated. Three participants were professional game designers working with, or previously having worked for, established game studios in Finland, and one participant was a game design student in their final year at a Finnish university. At the very beginning of the workshop, all workshop participants were given a few minutes to read the privacy notice (Appendix A), having the opportunity to read about the workshop purpose, procedures and data collection, followed by a space for questions and a kind request to leave the workshop in case they did not agree with the privacy notice. All participants gave their consent, and the workshop began.

The intended outcome of the workshop was to ideate the game prototype around the results of the needs analysis, focusing on the game concept and the overall narrative. The discussion was facilitated by our research team, with answers expressed vocally, as well as captured on a Flinga board. Neither audio or video recording was made of the session.

The questions presented below were written on the Flinga board and, to facilitate the design process, asked by the facilitator of the meeting. Participants could approach them in any order they liked; however, with the aim of supporting the exchange among the participants, they were asked to share their thoughts and opinions aloud while answering them.

Questions:

- Think of a game where you had to work with others to succeed. How did it make you feel included, or not?
 - How can the narrative celebrate the diversity of the players?
 - How can we use the narrative to create a sense of accomplishment through collaboration?
 - What's the mission or main goal of the game?
 - What overarching story or theme could motivate youth to connect and collaborate?
 - What kind of world are players in?
- How can we incentivise players to collaborate with others?
- What key actions will players perform in the game?
- How can we ensure inclusion?
- How can we reward or reinforce social connections?

These questions helped gather creative ideas around the given topic and appropriate narrative themes, visuals and game mechanics. In summary, *the themes of space and escape permeated the discussion, framing the starting concepts of navigating the unknown, meeting otherness and teaming up for a common goal.*

The screen captions from Flinga with all the answers and the workshop outcomes can be found in Appendix B.

After this workshop, we were better equipped with understanding how to approach the prototype and make the game engaging, as well as what kind of concepts and narratives we could utilise to achieve our goal.

3.3 Second Design Workshop

Finally, the second design workshop took place among the Gamification Group (GG) members, bringing together GAMEHEARTS researchers and GG's internal team of designers and developers. The workshop took place on October 21, 2024 at the GG premises, lasting approximately four hours and welcoming four participants and one facilitator.

Considering that the narrative setting was pre-decided on a space theme, the aim of this workshop was to further ideate on and work out the details regarding the game characters, environment and the in-game features, in line with the theoretical framework. For this, we used the so-called "gamestorming" technique, followed by the development of the narrative arcs.

The first part of the workshop was about the story characters and the environment. This segment was conducted in four sessions, each lasting 10 minutes. Within this time, each participant had to think of and write down on post-it notes their ideas related to a given prompt. After the time was up, the group gathered and decided together which ideas should be kept and which discarded (or adjusted), thus gradually creating a final set of character traits and in-game scenarios that will be prototyped.

- 1) Initially, we all wrote down ideas regarding the **key traits or characteristics** we envisioned for the protagonist. All of the ideas shared could be summarised into four main categories: the protagonist is someone who is *lonely and uncertain*, however *determined and interesting*. They enjoy *engaging in discussions and giving opinions*, are *social and friendly*.
- 2) Once these traits and characters were set, it was time to ideate on the character's **name and description, as well their backstory**. Following the space theme, the chosen protagonist's name was *Xeno*; *Xeno has a morphing body and can be anything, as well as can change their features in different scenarios*. As for the backstory, *they have been sent on a mission to save their species; however, it was too late and once back home, Xeno finds that everyone else is gone*.
- 3) The chosen backstory leads towards the conceptualisation of the **environment and the world theme**. The space theme and the backstory guided us to ideate towards a *space station, that is abandoned, but that has served as a research centre*. Also, *in this environment, every once in a while, a strange noise can be heard*.

- 4) The final part, before proceeding to the narrative arcs, was about **conflicts and turning points** that will drive the story. The team came up with the following: *The noise in the centre comes from one of the research capsules – in it, Xeno finds another creature and discovers that they are not alone after all.*

Figure 2. A prototypical narrative arc. (Lee et al., 2010)

Appendix C shows the prototype design process, with all the resulting ideas and materials presented in images.

The narrative arc model used in the workshop was divided into three acts: Act I (Opening), corresponding to the exposition, Act II (Middle), corresponding to complication and escalation, leading towards the climax, and Act III (End), corresponding to the resolution (see Appendix C). Translating the ideas and concepts resulting from the previous part of the workshop, the narrative arc looked like the following:

Act I (character → setting)

Act II (conflict → rising action #1 → rising action #2)

Act III (climax → falling action → resolution)

In other words, Act I describes the character and the set environment, as well as provides background information on Xeno (as shown above). Act II starts with the conflict, i.e. Xeno's encounter with the new character, their first reaction and interaction. Rising actions that lead towards the climax are guided by the notion of Connection (see: 2.2 Theoretical framework), that is, the players would need to interact with the characters, the environment (and possibly each other) in order to build bonds, find out what happened and progress in the story. Act III starts with the climax, in this case, a piece of information that is needed to unlock the next segment of the game. Xeno now knows that they are not alone and have built a bond with a new character. As a resolution, a reward in the form of a "Connections" badge is presented.

The next section provides more information on the narrative and the core mechanics and how it was implemented in the prototype.

4. Prototypes

The PYD-framework posits that person-context interaction through youth programs cultivates the 5 C's: competence, confidence, connection, character, and caring (Lerner, 2009). Our design gamifies this process by prompting players to explore, utilise and improve the 5 C's through the game, together with other youth in their relevant physical context. The 5 C's are represented through the narrative storyline and the characters. Each arc of the story deals with one skill respectively, and when completed, the players are awarded the skill. The completion of the game requires collection of all 5 C's. As such, players are expected to explore, utilise and improve the 5 C's while playing. The video game is a hybrid game which couples' real-life interaction and collaboration with virtual feedback. Players need to collaborate in the same space in order to proceed in the game, thereby practising the relevant skill together and seeing it mirrored in the digital game. The utilisation of the skills in question will be designed to address the needs identified by youth workers in the needs analysis. They will be modelled in the narrative story and the real-life interactions will practise that skill towards the need. A moderator will oversee the real-life interactions to facilitate the proceeding in the game. The prototype shows the central concept of the gameplay and is based around the skill of connection.

The narrative concept is based around the character of Xeno, who is an alien in space. Xeno has been sent on an exploration mission by the planet's research centre to find a new natural resource for his species to save them from existential doom. The mission unfortunately fails, and Xeno has returned to their home planet to deliver the devastating news. Upon returning to the research centre, Xeno finds it abandoned with next to no clear expectation on what has happened and where everyone has disappeared. It seems that Xeno is the only alien left on the planet. Xeno unexpectedly finds a human in the research centre with whom they will have to interact and collaborate to be able to understand what has happened and what to do next.

The wireframes were first sketched out on paper through storyboarding and later adapted to a digital prototype using Canva. Icons used were taken from Canva and the Power Point-library. External assets and tools were used as follows. From itch.io: Seamless Space Background by Screaming Brain Studios (prototype pictures 1, 5-9), Pixel Planet Generator by Deep Fold (prototype picture 1) and Void Ship by Fozzlecc (prototype picture 1). From craftpix.net: Free Robot Pixel Art (prototype pictures 2-4, 8). The research centre and the creature images were generated through ChatGPT¹ (prototype pictures 2-4).

¹ The images generated by ChatGPT for these prototypes are intended solely as preliminary visuals to inspire discussion and ideation with youth participants and will not be included in the final game. Using AI-generated content in this early conceptual stage allows the project team to explore ideas quickly and visually. However, it is essential to acknowledge that AI-generated images may carry biases or lack the nuanced representation that a fully developed design requires. Therefore, these visuals are used here only to facilitate conversation and ensure that youth perspectives guide the creative direction moving forward.

Prototype picture 1:
Story introduction.

Prototype pictures 2 and 3:
Play environment and Xeno in the abandoned research centre. Players can explore surroundings and find out clues. Xeno hears muffled, distressed sounds from a capsule. Players can tap to explore.

Prototype picture 4:
Encounter with the new creature and prompt of "connection" story arc. Xeno and the creature will have to connect and create a positive bond to collaborate. They might also have to create bonds with others to receive more information and progress.

Prototype picture 5-9:
 Players are instructed on a real-life exercise. When the real-life exercise is complete, moderator taps to approve and all players move forward in the story through receiving more information on what has happened, what to do next or by progressing in the story. When all exercises are completed and the narrative arc settles down, players will have explored, utilized and improved connection through the game and earned the skill of CONNECTION, which will appear in players' inventory.

5. Next Steps

The immediate next step for game development is organising a series of co-design workshops with a larger scope. Participating stakeholders will consist of representatives from the target group (youth taking part in youth work services), youth workers, game designers, game developers, and other potential relevant stakeholders, for example researchers in the areas of youth development. Here, the practical needs and challenges of youth and youth workers will play a large role in influencing the narrative gameplay. By involving all these parties in a co-design process, we ensure that the game is inclusive to different players and targets relevant needs in appropriate ways. As a result of this second, more comprehensive workshop series, we will aim to have a fleshed-out gameplay and story that works in tandem real-life interactions.

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7. Appendices

APPENDIX A: PRIVACY NOTICE

WORKSHOP DESCRIPTION AND PRIVACY NOTICE WORKSHOP “GAMEFUL TOOL FOR YOUTH INCLUSION”

After you have read this notice, you will be given an opportunity to ask questions about the workshop. After that, you will be asked to give your verbal consent. **Please note that to participate in the workshop, you must give your acceptance to the privacy notice.**

Please bear in mind that this workshop is a research-based event, and that collected data might be presented in an academic publication. In this document, you will find more information about the event and how the information you provide will be collected and processed.

Purpose of the workshop

The purpose of this workshop is to engage industry experts in ideation and conceptual design towards the development of a gameful tool. The expected outcome of the workshop is a rough gameful concept and idea on which to base a prototype, which is part of a deliverable in the project “GameHeArtS” (HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01-06, grant agreement 101132543). The ideas and outcomes of this workshop might be incorporated in a video game as part of the same project, and in future academic publications.

For this purpose, a workshop lasting up to two hours is conducted in which the participants engage in ideation and concept design in a guided discussion by Tampere University’s researchers.

How is the workshop data collected?

The workshop will take place remotely via the Teams platform. The workshop data and final conceptual outcome will be stored electronically, with the purpose of being used to build a prototype.

Benefits and risks related to the workshop

Participants will not receive any monetary nor other compensations for their participation.

There are no health, social, economic, or personal data processing risks associated with the methodology used in this workshop. Low risk exists when it comes to the possibility of external persons identifying participants. Measures to prevent this from happening include storing and handling personal data in accordance with the Tampere University recommendations and regulations.

Confidentiality, data processing and storage

The research data collected about you will be handled confidentially in accordance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation and the Finnish Data Protection Act. Collected contact email information will be securely stored and used solely for the purpose of facilitating the workshop.

The privacy protection of individuals is assured in scientific and other publications

The research files and the data collected for the workshop will be pseudonymised and preserved at Tampere University for a maximum of one year, after which they will be destroyed.

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Voluntariness

Participation in the workshop is completely voluntary and you can withdraw your participation at any time. You can also suspend your participation for a period of your choosing. Refusing or suspending participation will not affect any treatment you may need later. If the participant decides to withdraw, all data that was previously collected would be destroyed.

Privacy in research publications and communications about the research

In scientific and other publications, any and all data collected from the participants will be presented in an aggregated form. Research results will be available in scientific publications.

Using the data for other than research and further study

All data collected from the participants will only be used by projects' researchers for research purposes and publication of scientific findings.

Further information

For more information about the workshop, you may contact Ylva Sundvik.

Researcher's contact details

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APPENDIX B: FIRST DESIGN WORKSHOP: FLINGA SCREEN CAPTURES

Answers to question 1.

Answers to question 2 and the corresponding sub-questions.

Answers to the final set of questions.

Drawing connections between all answers from the previous questions and deciding on the overarching narrative and mechanics.

APPENDIX C: SECOND DESIGN WORKSHOP: IMAGES AND DESIGN DOCUMENTS

Workshop warm-up and initial ideation.

Outcomes of the first session: protagonist's traits.

Outcomes of the third session: game environment.

Outcomes of the fourth and final session: conflicts and turning points in the narrative.

Workshop session outline with the selected concepts.

Narrative arc model and preliminary storyline.

DISCLAIMER

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